

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO – Single-Family Houses in Boston, MA

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Abstract

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization (BESOO) is a system of online internet programs that calculates temperatures, Heat Index, energy, and other parameters for various cases and conditions based on input values.

The current version is for ambient temperature, relative humidity, and solar radiation in Boston, MA, USA.

The program allows selection of the thickness of each layer of the outside wall, the level of ventilation, and the building orientation every 22.5 degrees.

Version 611 calculates room air temperature and Heat Index without space heating and air conditioning.

Version 612 calculates the thermal energy required for space heating during the heating period and for cooling during the cooling period.

In addition, the program calculates Thermal Time Constant, TTC, based on the input data.

Despite the typical design of single-family houses in Massachusetts, the program allows the addition of a concrete layer to the outside wall.

The online internet programs based on this work are available on (free, no login required):

nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/611B

nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/612B

nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/644B

Glossary

Ave	average
BL	baseline
CHI	Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C, 79.9°F
CL	Cold Limit, room air comfortable temperature low limit, °C
cp	specific heat, J/kg,°C
dir	outside wall direction
HI	Heat Index – air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, °C
HIO	Heat Index not in summer defined season, °C
Lo	length of outside wall, m
OSB	Oriented Strand Board, a strong panel made of pieces of wood bonded with urea-formaldehyde
PS	Polystyrene Foam
PVC	Poly Vinyl Chloride, external siding of the outside wall of the building
r	thermal resistance of a layer in outside wall, m ² ,°C/W
R	total thermal resistance of all layers of outside wall without laminar layers, m ² ,°C/W
R-30	thermal insulation of outside wall level 30 according to US standards, hr*ft ² *F/BTU
RH	relative humidity of air, %

SE	global solar radiation, W/m ²
Ta	ambient (outside) air temperature, °C
Th	thickness of the layer in outside wall, m
Tr	room air temperature, °C
TTC	Thermal Time Constant, hours

Energy Units

Generally, this work is in metric units. Energy is expressed in kWh and power in Watts.

Calculations of the Heat Index involve degrees Fahrenheit.

The level of thermal insulation in the US, like R-30, is measured in imperial units: hr*ft²*°F/BTU.

Time is ET (GMT-5).

Heat Index - HI

The Heat Index (HI) is the air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent, expressed in °C (or °F).

Heat Index is the “feel like” air temperature that combines the actual temperature and humidity.

Heat Index is described in detail in the publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [1]. The publication [1] includes also the Heat Index formula.

Comfort Heat Index - CHI

The publication "*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*" [1] defined the comfort level of the Heat Index as a Comfort Heat Index (CHI) equal to 26.6°C (79.9°F).

Heat index above the CHI causes discomfort [1], and below the CHI or OCAC causes overcooling discomfort [2].

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning

Cooling below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) not only wastes energy but also causes severe discomfort and health hazards for many people. In this work, a Heat Index (HI) above or below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is considered equally uncomfortable conditions.

Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning is described in the publication "*Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning*" [2].

The publication [1] introduces the Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning (OCAC), a thermostat setting that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

The average OCAC is 25.5°C.

Accordingly, the default input value for air conditioning temperature setting in version 612 and 644 is 25.5°C.

Discomfort Heat Index - DHI

Discomfort Heat Index (DHI) is the room air Heat Index (HI) above the Comfort Heat Index (CHI).

Formula 1 - Discomfort Heat Index – DHI, °C

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DHI} &= \text{HI} - \text{CHI} \\ \text{CHI} &= 26.6^\circ\text{C} \\ \text{DHI} &= \text{HI} - 26.6^\circ\text{C} \end{aligned}$$

Cold Discomfort - CD

Cold Discomfort (CD) is the room air temperature below the comfort level as defined by the home tenants. The default CD value in this work is 18°C.

Formula 2 - Cold Discomfort – CD, °C

$$\text{CD} = \text{CL} - \text{Tr}$$

CD	Cold Discomfort, °C
CL	Cool Limit, room air comfortable temperature low limit, as defined by the home tenants (default=18°C)
Tr	room air temperature, °C

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Programs - BESOO

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization (BESOO) is a system of online internet programs that calculates temperatures, Heat Index and energy for various cases and conditions determined in the input section of the program.

Generally, all BESOO versions are based on the research "*Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESO*" by Joseph Nowarski and Prof. G. L. Esterson,

presented at the First Joint Conference of International Simulation Societies, 22-25 August 1994, ETH Zurich, Switzerland [3].

The BESOO program was successfully validated using Thermal Time Constant (TTC) method as described in the publication [4].

The current versions (611, 612 and 644) are based on the following BESOO programs:

- v511 – no space heating or cooling, room air Heat Index [5]
- v512 - thermal energy for space heating and cooling [6]
- v522 - limited period for cooling and heating
- v542 – cooling only all the year round
- v544 – optional 10-minute results

Application of version 512 involved cooling at a lower temperature than space heating. This resulted in very high energy consumption and power for heating and cooling when switching between cooling and heating, considering not only the room air volume, but also the thermal mass of the walls. To avoid such a situation, the input heat-on temperature was automatically reduced below the cool-on setting.

This was fixed in version 522 by defining separate heating and cooling periods, which shortened the overcooling period.

To analyze the overcooling impact for the whole year, version 542 was dedicated to cooling only.

Version 544 significantly reduced the simulation time by suspending the 10-minute results on the screen and in a CSV file. This version was also for cooling only.

The current version (612) determines heating and cooling periods and days of separation between the both periods.

All previous BESOO versions up to 544 were limited to two locations - Jerusalem and Tel Aviv. Versions 611, 612 and 644 are intended for multiple locations. This work is for Boston, MA only.

Ambient Air Temperature, Relative Humidity, and Solar Radiation Datasets

Ambient air temperature, air relative humidity (RH), and solar global radiation datasets are from the website “Open-Meteo - Historical Weather API” [7-11]. The records are every hour and every day. The datasets are for the years 2023 and 2024.

All BESOO programs require 10-minute meteorological data. The 10-minute data were determined using linear interpolation between adjacent hours.

The site [7-11] also includes solar radiation at any tilt angle and any direction (azimuth). This allows the determination of the conversion factors between global solar radiation on a horizontal surface and the radiation on the building walls. The horizontal surface has 0 degrees tilt angle and the vertical walls of the building 90 degrees.

All BESOO programs apply hourly solar gain conversion factors for 16 directions (azimuth) for every month. To obtain solar gain on the vertical outside walls of the building, the global solar radiation is multiplied by the conversion factor depending on the outside wall orientation, month and hour. The conversion factors are available on the website [12].

The meteorological data are for the location 42.355, -71.1291 in Boston, MA, USA.

Starting the simulation on 1st January midnight involves a big difference between the ambient air temperature and the room air and the building walls temperature. To avoid a long period of stabilization of the simulation results (depending on the Thermal Time Constant – TTC of the building), the simulation starts between the heating and cooling period, while on the first day of the simulation the room air and the walls temperature equals to the daily average temperature of the same day, till the hour when the actual ambient temperature reaches the day average.

Heating and Cooling Seasons

Determination of Heating and Cooling seasons is very important for building energy simulation programs, like BESOO.

Application of version 512 involved cooling at a lower temperature than the space heating. This resulted in very high energy consumption and power for heating and cooling when switching between cooling and heating, considering not only the room air volume, but also the thermal mass of the walls.

To avoid such a situation, the heating and cooling were limited to specific dates in BESOO version 522.

This was also a reason to exclude the space heating from the BESOO simulation programs in versions 542 and 544, as they were dedicated to the overcooling issue.

The current versions of BESOO program (611 and 612) will apply specific heating and cooling seasons based on the following assumptions:

- the most popular cooling temperature is 24°C, therefore the cooling season starts when the 10-days average ambient temperature rises above 24°C
- the heating season starts when the 10-days average ambient temperature drops below 18°C
- a few days separation period between heating and cooling seasons

Chart 1 - Ambient temperature in Boston 2023-2024 10-day averages, °C

the dates are at the end of the 10-day average periods

Table 1 - Heating and Cooling simulation seasons for Boston

	from	to	days
Simulation	12/09/23	11/09/24	365
Heating	12/09/23	21/05/24	252
Cooling	31/05/24	11/09/24	103

On the first day of the simulation, the temperature of the outside wall layers and the room air temperature will be set to the average temperature of the first day until the time when the actual ambient temperature is above the average temperature.

Table 2 - First day of the simulation

first day date	12/09/23
average temperature of the first day	21.95
hour of the average temperature	8:40

The application of BESOO version 644B, which is for cooling only, allows the determination of the cooling period in Boston based on Cool-On temperature. The simulation period in version 644B is 28/01/23-27/01/24, considering the average of the coldest 10 days during which air conditioning should not be needed.

Table 3 - Cooling periods in Boston, MA according to version 644B

Cool-On °C	Start	End	days d/y	hours hr/y	Overcooling °C
25.5	05/07/23	08/09/23	65	75	0
24	25/06/23	09/09/23	76	222	2.29
23	01/06/23	12/09/23	103	400	3.34
22	28/05/23	12/09/23	107	718	4.34
21	13/05/23	05/10/23	145	1,026	5.42
20	13/04/23	28/10/23	198	1,380	6.50

Cool-On thermostat setting of air conditioning, °C
 Overcooling difference between Comfort Heat Index (CHI) and actual Heat Index (HI) of the room air [°C/°F]
 CHI Comfort Heat Index = 26.6°C, 79.9°F
 HI Heat Index – room air humidity discomfort temperature equivalent [°C/°F]
 hours air conditioning operating hours according to Cool-On thermostat setting, hr/y

The above table indicates overlap between heating and cooling seasons for air conditioning Cool-On temperatures below 24°C.

For simulation of air conditioning overcooling temperatures (Cool-On < 25.5°C), it is recommended to use version 644B of the BESOO program, which is for cooling only all year round.

The Building

The calculations are for a single section of the building, not for the entire building or not for individual rooms; a single section of the building is considered one room. The default size of a single section is 100 m² (10m x 10m). It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring sections of the building is the same as in the tested section.

Chart 2 - Building and the selected section for the simulation

In the example of the above building, the simulation should be done separately for each of the four sections of the building.

The optimum building orientation was analyzed in the publication "*Optimization of Residential Building Orientation in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv using Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO*" [14].

According to this publication, the best building orientation is ESS+SWW. Therefore, the default input for building orientation in all BESOO programs is ESS+SWW.

Outside Wall Layers

The heat flow is from outside the building to inside. In cases where the heat flow is in the opposite direction, the value of the heat flow [Q] is negative.

Table 4 - Outside wall layers of a single family house in Massachusetts

Layer #	Layer	Material
	Outside air	
0	Outside laminar layer	
1	Outer layer	Siding, PVC
2	Outside insulation	Polystyrene Foam (PS) R-5
3	Central layer	OSB
		or Concrete *
4	Inside insulation	Glasswool
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Wallboard
6	Inside laminar layer	
	Room air	

* Concrete is not used for outside walls for single-family houses in Massachusetts. It may be applied in the BESOO simulation to analyze “what if” option

Table 5 - Outside wall layers data

Layer #	Layer	Material	Th	Density	cp	Conductivity	R
Units			m	kg/m ³	J/kg,°C	W/m,°C	m ² ,°C/W
			Th	Rho	cp	λ	r
	Outside air						
0	Outside laminar layer						
1	Siding	PVC	0.0011	1,430	900	0.1500	0.007
2	Outer insulation	PS R-5	0.0282	30	1440	0.0320	0.881
3	Central layer	OSB	0.0127	600	1980	0.1300	0.098
		or Concrete *	0.0000	2400	970	2.1000	0.000
4	Inner insulation	Glasswool	0.1550	24	860	0.0440	3.522
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Wallboard	0.0127	900	1080	0.2100	0.060
6	Inside laminar layer						
	Room air						
	Total		0.210		1,321		4.75
	R(SI) without laminar layers					m ² ,°C/W	4.57
	R(US)					hr*ft ² *F/BTU	25.94

* If a concrete layer is applied (Th>0), the OSB layer is excluded from the simulation.

- Th layer thickness, m
- cp specific heat, J/kg,°C
- r thermal resistance of the layer, m²,°C/W
- R total thermal resistance of outside wall without laminar layers, hr*ft²*F/BTU

The 2026 Massachusetts state requirement is $R > 30 \text{ hr} \cdot \text{ft}^2 \cdot \text{F} / \text{BTU}$ (R-30). The above table results in a total thermal resistance of $25.94 \text{ hr} \cdot \text{ft}^2 \cdot \text{F} / \text{BTU}$. Therefore, additional insulation is required for R-30. The insulation (PS) will be added to the outer insulation layer (Layer 2). Since R-5 does not meet the required R-30, the outer insulation layer thickness must be increased accordingly.

Table 6 - Corrected outside wall layers data according to MA State requirements for 2026 (R-30)

Layer #	Layer	Material	Th	Density	cp	Conductivity	R
Units			m	kg/m ³	J/kg, °C	W/m, °C	m ² , °C/W
			Th	Rho	cp	λ	r
	Outside air						
0	Outside laminar layer						0.040
1	Siding	PVC	0.0011	1,430	900	0.1500	0.007
2	Outer insulation	PS R-10	0.0564	30	1440	0.0320	1.761
3	Central layer	OSB	0.0127	600	1980	0.1300	0.098
		Or					
		Concrete	0	2400	970	2.1000	0
4	Inner insulation	Glasswool	0.1550	24	860	0.0440	3.522
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Wallboard	0.0127	900	1080	0.2100	0.060
6	Inside laminar layer						0.145
	Room air						
	Total		0.238		1,325		5.63
	R(SI) without laminar layers					m ² , °C/W	5.45
	R(US)					hr ² ·ft ² ·F/BTU	30.94

To meet the R-30 requirement for the outside wall thermal resistance, the outer insulation (Layer 2) thickness was increased from the standard 28.2 mm to 56.4 mm.

Input Parameters and Default Values

Table 7 - BESOO v612 input parameters and default values for a single-family house in Boston

choose direction of part 1:

choose direction of part 2:

Heat On temperature	20 °C
Cool On temperature	25.5 °C
infiltration - number of changes per hour	0.1 V/hr
ventilation - number of changes per hour	7 V/hr
Summer activation of ventilation Δ (Troom - Ta) >	1 °C
Winter activation of ventilation Δ (Ta - Troom) >	1 °C
height between floors (outside)	3.00 m
room height (inside)	2.65 m
floor length of outside wall part 1	10 m
floor length of outside wall part 2	10 m
outer layer (1) siding - PVC thickness	0.0011 m
outer insulation layer (2) PS R-10 thickness	0.0564 m
central layer (3) OSB thickness	0.0127 m
or central layer (3) concrete thickness	0 m
inner insulation layer (4) glasswool thickness	0.1550 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum wallboard thickness	0.0127 m
do you want each 10min results on screen and CSV file 52,000 lines (takes time)? (1=Yes, 0=No)	0

Fix Parameters

Table 8 - Fix parameters part 1

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Integration Interval	dtau	10	seconds
air density	RhoA	1.204529	kg/m ³
air specific heat	cpa	1007	J/kg,°C
absorption coefficient of solar radiation on building walls	AbF	0.53	

Table 9 - Fix parameters part 2 for Boston

layer	material	Rho [kg/m ³]	λ [W/m,°C]	cp [J/kg,°C]
layer 1	Siding PVC	1,430	0.1500	900
layer 2	outer insulation PS	30	0.0320	1440
layer 3	OSB	600	0.1300	1980
	or			
	concrete	2400	2.1	970
layer 4	inner insulation glasswool	24	0.0440	860
layer 5	Gypsum Wallboard	900	0.2100	1080

Initial Values

Table 10 - Initial values

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
initial room air temperature	Tr	21.9	°C
initial temperatures of all layers of the outside wall	To1, To3, To5	21.9	°C

The initial temperature of the outside wall layers and of the room air is the average of ambient air temperature on 12 Sep 2023 - 21.9°C.

Simulation Results

In all 6xx versions the simulation results are in the following form:

- Results table at the end of the internet results page
- CSV file with hourly results (in version 612 and 644 only)
- CSV file with daily results
- Optional table on the internet results page. This table includes more than 52,000 lines showing some results every 10 minutes and others every hour
- Optional CSV file with the 10-minute results as on the internet page in the original resolution (more precise). The data in this file are related to the last Integration Interval ($d\tau$) cycle and are not the 10-minute averages or totals.

The CSV files may be downloaded from the internet results page.

BESOO v611 Simulation Results

BESOO version 611 is without space heating and air conditioning.

Table 11 - BESOO 611 (no space heating and air conditioning) results table for default input

20/03/2026 15:31:08 ET, Integration Interval 10sec https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/611B			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 611B, v611B01 no heating or cooling, Heat Index (CHI) - Boston			
Thermal Time Constant	30.42	hours	TTC
start day	20230912		
last day	20240910		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
thermal discomfort hours	6247	hr/y	71%
Winter			
Cold Limit (CL)	18	°C	
winter starts	20230912		
winter ends	20240530		
Ave room air temperature in winter	9.97	°C	AveTr
duration of winter	6288	hr/y	72%
maximum room air temperature in winter °C / day / hour	29.74	20240522	17:00
minimum room air temperature in winter °C / day / hour	-8.23	20240121	9:40
Ave room air temperature below Comfort Limit CL in winter	7.94	°C	AveDnT
Cool Discomfort CD in winter	10.06	°C	CD
duration of Cool Discomfort CD in winter	5365	hr/y	61%
Ave room air temperature below Comfort Limit CL in summer	16.15	°C	AveSDnT
duration of Cool Discomfort CD in summer	675	hr/y	8%
total Cool Discomfort CD hours	6040	hr/y	69%
HI = Heat Index			
summer starts	20240531		
summer ends	20240910		
Ave Heat Index (HIC) in summer	20.45	°C	AveHIC
duration of summer	2472	hr/y	28%
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in summer	28.96	°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in summer	135	hr/y	2%
Ave HIO = (HI>CHI) not in summer	28.84	°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI not in summer	72	hr/y	1%
Max Heat Index in summer °C	33.39	20240716	19:30
Max HIO not in summer °C	34.06	20240522	18:00
total duration of HI above Comfort Heat Index (CHI)	207	hr/y	2%
total Heat Index (HI) above Comfort Heat Index (CHI)	28.92	°C	AveHIup
Discomfort Heat Index - DHI	2.32	°C	DHI
Ventilation			
ventilation in winter	261	hr/y	52%
ventilation in cooling season - summer	237	hr/y	48%
total ventilation hours	497	hr/y	6%
Thermal comfort hours			
comfort hours in Winter above CL	923	hr/y	11%
comfort hours in Summer below CHI	2337	hr/y	27%
total thermal comfort hours	2513	hr/y	29%
thermal comfort hours without ventilation	2016	hr/y	23%

Table 12 - Small part of 10-minute CSV file for the lowest room temperature (total 52,560 lines)

1	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	
1	nowagree Boston														
2	Outside W 20/03/2026 16:0 dtau=10 sec														
3	please note that the data in this file are related to the last Integration Interval (dtau) cycle and are not the 10 minutes averages or totals														
	day	date	hr	min	Ta	RH	SE [W/m2]	Solar Gain [W]	To1	To3	To5	Tr	QoR [W]	Heat Index [C]	
18906	132	20240121	6	20	-11.2667	61.66667	0	0	-11.214	-9.02831	-7.78436	-7.83277	14.63995	-10.95030123	
18907	132	20240121	6	30	-11.3	61.5	0	0	-11.2474	-9.06272	-7.81461	-7.86298	14.6304	-10.98789085	
18908	132	20240121	6	40	-11.3333	61.33333	0	0	-11.2807	-9.09706	-7.84491	-7.89326	14.6255	-11.02555114	
18909	132	20240121	6	50	-11.3667	61.16667	0	0	-11.3141	-9.13134	-7.87526	-7.9236	14.6227	-11.06327448	
18910	132	20240121	7	0	-11.4	61	0	0	-11.3474	-9.16556	-7.90565	-7.95399	14.62093	-11.10105681	
18911	132	20240121	7	10	-11.25	60	7.233333	0	-11.2017	-9.19623	-7.93576	-7.98205	14.00809	-11.15803341	
18912	132	20240121	7	20	-11.1	59	14.46667	0	-11.0558	-9.2231	-7.96516	-8.00857	13.14214	-11.21332138	
18913	132	20240121	7	30	-10.95	58	21.7	0	-10.9099	-9.24626	-7.99365	-8.03389	12.18041	-11.26727774	
18914	132	20240121	7	40	-10.8	57	28.93333	0	-10.7639	-9.26583	-8.02116	-8.05812	11.18897	-11.32004127	
18915	132	20240121	7	50	-10.65	56	36.16667	0	-10.6178	-9.2819	-8.04763	-8.08131	10.1954	-11.37165949	
18916	132	20240121	8	0	-10.5	55	43.4	2503.402999	-8.45678	-9.25547	-8.07282	-8.10343	9.265689	-11.422106	
18917	132	20240121	8	10	-10.4	54	73.4	4233.865902	-6.96557	-9.19659	-8.0964	-8.12495	8.639835	-11.47189055	
18918	132	20240121	8	20	-10.3	53	103.4	5964.328804	-5.47367	-9.1077	-8.11821	-8.14541	8.228992	-11.52050589	
18919	132	20240121	8	30	-10.2	52	133.4	7694.791707	-3.98109	-8.98975	-8.13804	-8.16447	7.991097	-11.56758285	
18920	132	20240121	8	40	-10.1	51	163.4	9425.254609	-2.48784	-8.84365	-8.1557	-8.18185	7.90603	-11.61281808	
18921	132	20240121	8	50	-10	50	193.4	11155.71751	-0.99394	-8.67026	-8.17097	-8.19732	7.963005	-11.65594317	
18922	132	20240121	9	0	-9.9	49	223.4	9564.010881	-2.17329	-8.52234	-8.18395	-8.21069	8.082772	-11.69679537	
18923	132	20240121	9	10	-9.68333	48	247.9167	10613.59757	-1.11358	-8.3613	-8.19461	-8.22045	7.815234	-11.73360924	
18924	132	20240121	9	20	-9.46667	47	272.4333	11663.18426	-0.05341	-8.18272	-8.20254	-8.22711	7.429795	-11.76703811	
18925	132	20240121	9	30	-9.25	46	296.95	12712.77095	1.00716	-7.98715	-8.2075	-8.23079	7.043984	-11.79720324	
18926	132	20240121	9	40	-9.03333	45	321.4667	13762.35764	2.068118	-7.77509	-8.20933	-8.23151	6.706014	-11.82410201	
18927	132	20240121	9	50	-8.81667	44	345.9833	14811.94434	3.129453	-7.54703	-8.2079	-8.22919	6.43491	-11.84766825	
18928	132	20240121	10	0	-8.6	43	370.5	13016.10445	1.901	-7.3479	-8.20338	-8.22381	6.175353	-11.86785376	
18929	132	20240121	10	10	-8.35	42	333.33	385.1333	13530.1908	2.563444	-7.14494	-8.19593	-8.21501	5.770949	-11.87558906
18930	132	20240121	10	20	-8.1	41	666.67	399.7667	14044.27716	3.226109	-6.93417	-8.18541	-8.20303	5.327072	-11.87981384

- day # simulation day number starting with 0
- date date of ambient temperature, RH and solar radiation data, 8 digits – yyyymmdd
- hr/min hour:minute of ambient temperature and solar radiation data
- Ta ambient air temperature [°C]
- RH relative humidity [%]
- SE global solar radiation [W/m2]
- SE Gain gain of solar radiation on the building outside walls [W]
- To1 temperature at the middle of Layer 1, outer layer [°C]
- To3 temperature at the middle of Layer 3, central layer [°C]
- To5 temperature at the middle of Layer 5, inner layer [°C]
- Tr room air temperature [°C]
- QoR conduction heat transfer from the middle of Layer 5 to the room air [W]

Chart 3 - BESOO 611 (no space heating and air conditioning) ambient temperature Ta and room temperature Tr on 21 Jan 2024 [°C]

Chart 4 - BESOO 611 (no space heating and air conditioning) ambient temperature Ta, room temperature Tr and Heat Index HI on 22 May 2024 [°C]

BESOO v612 Simulation Results

Table 13 - BESOO 612 results table for default input

21/03/2026 15:39:27 ET, Integration Interval 10sec https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/612B			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 612B, v612B02 heating and cooling seasons, Comfort Heat Index (CHI) - Boston			
Thermal Time Constant	30.42	hours	TTC
Heat On	19	°C	HeatT
Cool On	25.5	°C	CoolT
start day	20230912		
last day	20240910		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
thermal energy for heating and cooling	1294	kWh/y thermal	100%
Space Heating			
heating start date	20230916		
heating end date	20240521		
space heating hours in the simulation period	5377	hr/y	61%
thermal energy for heating	1238	kWh/y thermal	96%
Max 10min Heat power [W thermal]	545	20240121	7:00
Cooling			
cooling start date	20240618		
cooling end date	20240828		
cooling hours in the simulation period	203	hr/y	2%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	21	kWh/y thermal	2%
quantity of condense during cooling	50	liter of water/y	
cooling energy for condense	35	kWh/y thermal	3%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	56	kWh/y thermal	4%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	211	20240716	16:00
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	267	20240716	19:00
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	449	20240716	17:50
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.78	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	206	hr/y	2%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	26.56	20240802	23:50
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	24.97	20240716	15:00
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours		°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	0	hr/y	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.78	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	206	hr/y	2%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI	28.21	°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	7	hr/y	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	28.9	20231003	18:30
Ventilation			
ventilation in heating season - winter	23	hr/y	10%
ventilation in cooling season - summer	212	hr/y	90%
ventilation between seasons	0	hr/y	0%
total ventilation hours	234	hr/y	3%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	8557	hr/y	98%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	8322	hr/y	95%
comfort hours without cooling, heating or ventilation	2945	hr/y	34%

BESOO v644 Simulation Results

Table 14 - BESOO 644 results table for default input

21/03/2026 12:07:33 ET			
nowagreen.ct.ws BESOO page 644B, v 644B01 unlimited cooling period, Comfort Heat Index (CHI)			
CoolT	25.5	°C	Cool On
URL	https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESO/644B		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	30.42	hours	TTC
start day	20230128		
last day	20240127		
simulation days	365		
simulation hours	8760		100%
Cooling			
cooling start date	20230705		
cooling end date	20230908		
cooling hours in the simulation period	75		1%
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	7	kWh thermal	36%
quantity of condense during cooling	18	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	13	kWh thermal	64%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	20	kWh thermal	100%
Max 10min Cool power [W thermal]	169	20230907	15:40
Max 10min power for condense [W thermal]	302	20230907	17:00
Max 10min power for cooling and for condense	456	20230907	17:00
HI = Heat Index			
Ave Heat Index (HI) in cooling hours	25.88	°C	AveHIC
duration of Heat Index in cooling hours	76	hr/y	1%
Max Heat Index in cooling hours °C	26.53	20230727	19:00
Min Heat Index in cooling hours °C	25.18	20230907	14:00
Ave Heat Index above Comfort HI (CHI) in cooling hours		°C	AveHICup
duration of Heat Index above CHI in cooling hours	0	hr/y	0%
Ave Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	25.88	°C	AveHICdn
duration of Heat Index below CHI in cooling hours	76	hr/y	1%
HIO = (HI>CHI) not in Cooling hours			
Ave HIO above CHI		°C	AveHIO
duration of HIO above CHI	0	hr/y	0%
Max HIO above CHI °C	0	0	0
Ventilation			
ventilation hours	316	hr/y	4%
Comfort hours			
comfort hours without cooling	8685	hr/y	99%
comfort hours without cooling or ventilation	8369	hr/y	96%

Table 15 - Overcooling discomfort and waste of energy

CoolT °C	Start	End	hr/y	E kWh/y th	Power Wth	Ave HI °C	Max HI	vent hr/y
25.5	20230705	20230908	75	20	456	25.88	26.53	316
25.0	20230705	20230908	111	30	480	25.35	26.02	312
24.0	20230625	20230909	222	59	522	24.31	24.99	299
23.0	20230601	20230912	400	104	558	23.26	23.90	280
22.0	20230528	20230912	718	172	590	22.26	22.87	254
21.0	20230513	20231005	1,026	251	619	21.18	21.77	229
20.0	20230413	20231028	1,380	344	646	20.10	20.67	201
19.0	20230413	20231028	1,738	451	672	18.99	19.57	171
18.0	20230413	20231028	2,036	562	695	17.88	18.47	142
17.0	20230412	20231028	2,330	679	717	16.76	17.37	114
16.0	20230411	20231028	2,614	799	737	15.64	16.27	86

CoolT thermostat setting Cool-on, °C
 Start start of cooling period
 End end of cooling period
 hr/y hours of air conditioning operation per year
 E thermal energy for cooling and condense, kWh/y th
 Power air conditioning output maximum power for 10 minutes period of room temperature change to CoolT, Wth
 Ave HI average Heat Index in cooling hours, °C
 Max HI maximum Heat Index in cooling hours, °C
 vent ventilation hours, hr/y

Table 16 - Increased cooling hours with overcooling

CoolT °C	hr/y	Δ/°C	Δ to BL
25.5	75		BL
25.0	111	48%	48%
24.0	222	100%	196%
23.0	400	80%	433%
22.0	718	80%	857%
21.0	1,026	43%	1268%
20.0	1,380	35%	1740%
19.0	1,738	26%	2217%
18.0	2,036	17%	2615%
17.0	2,330	14%	3007%
16.0	2,614	12%	3385%
Min		12%	
Ave per 1°C		45%	356%
Max		100%	

Table 17 - Change in energy consumption with overcooling

CoolT °C	E kWh/y	E th	Δ/°C	Δ to BL
25.5	20	100%		BL
25.0	30	150%	50%	50%
24.0	59	295%	97%	195%
23.0	104	520%	76%	420%
22.0	172	860%	65%	760%
21.0	251	1255%	46%	1155%
20.0	344	1720%	37%	1620%
19.0	451	2255%	31%	2155%
18.0	562	2810%	25%	2710%
17.0	679	3395%	21%	3295%
16.0	799	3995%	18%	3895%
Min			18%	
Ave per 1°C			47%	410%
Max			97%	

The publication “Increase in Air Conditioning Energy Consumption with Each Centigrade” [13] indicates 33%/°C average increase in energy consumption with each Centigrade. It seems that the reason for the higher value in Boston is the moderate ambient temperature in summer, resulting in a very low baseline (cooling at 25.5°C).

Impact of Thermal Mass on Thermal Comfort and Energy Consumption

Table 18 - BESOO 611 no space heating or cooling - addition of concrete layer in outside walls

Th m	TTC hr	W Ave Tr °C	Min Tr °C	Δ to BL °C	Ave HI °C	Δ to BL °C	Max HI °C	Δ to BL °C	Comfort hr/y	Δ to BL
0.000	30	9.97	-8.23	BL	28.96	BL	34.06	BL	2016	BL
0.010	34	9.97	-7.97	0.26	28.85	-0.11	33.24	-0.82	2034	1%
0.050	81	9.96	-6.20	2.03	28.46	-0.50	30.28	-3.78	2111	5%
0.100	141	9.96	-4.84	3.39	28.26	-0.70	29.66	-4.40	2150	7%
0.200	263	9.98	-3.58	4.65	28.14	-0.82	29.33	-4.73	2225	10%

- Th concrete layer thickness, m
- TTC Thermal Time Constant, hr
- W Ave Tr winter average room temperature when < °C
- Min Tr minimum room temperature, °C
- Δ to BL BL = Baseline is 0 m concrete layer thickness (no concrete layer)
- Ave HI average Heat Index above CHI, °C
- CHI Comfort Heat Index, 26.6°C (79.9°F)
- Max HI maximum Heat Index, °C
- Comfort comfort hours per year without ventilation, hr/y

Impact of concrete layer on thermal performance – BESOO 611:

- no impact on average room temperature below 18°C, which remains unbearably low (10°C) without space heating
- mitigation of the minimum room temperature
- minor impact on average Heat Index above CHI
- significant decrease in the maximum Heat Index
- some positive impact on comfort hours

Table 19 - BESOO 612 including space heating and cooling - addition of concrete layer in outside walls

Th m	TTC hr	E kWh/y th	Heat hr/y	Heat kWh/y th	Cool hr/y	Cool kWh/y th	Δ to BL	Comfort hr/y
0.000	30.42	1294	5377	1238	203	56	BL	2945
0.010	33.95	1296	5430	1245	198	50	-11%	2891
0.020	45.72	1283	5464	1241	192	42	-25%	2860
0.030	57.52	1276	5468	1238	190	38	-32%	2857
0.100	140.99	1251	5495	1226	166	24	-57%	2850
0.200	262.85	1230	5495	1214	134	16	-71%	2882

- Th concrete layer thickness, m
- TTC Thermal Time Constant, hr
- E thermal energy consumption for space heating and cooling, kWh/y th
- Δ to BL BL = Baseline is 0 m concrete layer thickness (no concrete layer)
- Comfort comfort hours per year without space heating, air conditioning or ventilation, hr/y

Effect of concrete layer on thermal performance – BESOO 612:

- significant energy savings for cooling: 57% with a 10 cm concrete layer, and 71% with 20 cm
- significant reduction in cooling hours
- minor negative impact on total comfort hours

Adding a concrete layer to exterior walls - conclusion

- energy savings of 57%-71% for cooling and slight energy savings for space heating
- maximum Heat Index without cooling can be reduced with a 20 cm concrete layer from 34°C to 29°C, which is a significant improvement in thermal comfort.

- o The concrete layer does not increase the total comfort hours in Boston.

Impact of Thermal Insulation on Thermal Comfort and Energy Consumption

Table 20 - BESOO 611 no space heating or cooling - change in outer thermal insulation thickness

R-L2	R-Wall	Th	TTC	W Ave Tr	Min Tr	Δ	Ave HI	Δ	Max HI	Δ	Comfort	Comfort
hr*ft2*F/BTU		m	hr	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	hr/y	
R-1	R-21	0.005640	16.30	9.76	-9.04	0.44	29.58		37.14		1986	99%
R-5	R-25	0.028200	22.46	9.94	-8.60	0.44	29.19	-0.39	35.49	-1.65	1987	99%
R-10	R-30	0.056400	30.42	9.97	-8.23	0.37	28.96	-0.23	34.06	-1.43	2016	100%
R-15	R-35	0.084600	38.68	9.97	-7.98	0.25	28.77	-0.19	33.34	-0.72	2047	102%
R-20	R-40	0.112800	47.24	9.97	-7.81	0.17	28.64	-0.13	32.90	-0.44	2065	102%

- R-L2 thermal resistance of Layer 2 - outer insulation, hr*ft2*°F/BTU
- R-Wall thermal resistance of outside wall, hr*ft2*°F/BTU
- Th outer insulation layer (Layer L2) thickness, m
- TTC Thermal Time Constant, hr
- W Ave Tr average room temperature below 18°C
- Min Tr minimum room temperature per year, °C
- Ave HI average Heat Index below CHI, °C
- CHI Comfort Heat Index, 26.6°C (79.9°F)
- Comfort comfort hours per year within 18°C and CHI, without ventilation, hr/y

Effect of external insulation thickness on thermal performance – BESOO 611:

- o no effect on the average room temperature below 18°C above R-30, which remains unbearably low (10°C) without space heating
- o slight improvement in the minimum room temperature
- o minor mitigation of average Heat Index above CHI
- o 1.2°C reduction in the maximum Heat Index
- o slight contribution to comfort hours

Table 21 - BESOO 612 including space heating and cooling - change in outer thermal insulation thickness

R-L2	R-Wall	Th	TTC	E	E	EC	ΔE/cm	Comfort	Comfort
hr*ft ² *F/BTU		m	hr	kWh/y th				hr/y	
R-1	R-21	0.00564	16.30	1587				3082	105%
R-2	R-22	0.01128	17.82	1541	119%		5.1%	3063	104%
R-3	R-23	0.01692	19.36	1499	116%		4.8%	3033	103%
R-4	R-24	0.02256	20.90	1461	113%		4.5%	3011	103%
R-5	R-25	0.02820	22.46	1426	110%		4.2%	2994	102%
R-10	R-30	0.05640	30.42	1294	100%	BL	3.3%	2945	100%
R-15	R-35	0.08460	38.68	1204	93%	7%	2.5%	2937	100%
		0.10000	43.32	1165	90%	10%	2.1%	2937	100%
R-20	R-40	0.11280	47.24	1137	88%	12%	1.9%	2944	100%

- R-L2 thermal resistance of Layer 2 - outer insulation, hr*ft²*F/BTU
- R-Wall thermal resistance of outside wall, hr*ft²*F/BTU
- Th outer insulation layer (Layer L2) thickness, m
- TTC Thermal Time Constant, hr
- E thermal energy consumption for space heating and cooling, kWh/y th
- EC Energy Conservation
- ΔE/cm contribution of 1 cm of outer insulation thickness to energy saving
- Comfort comfort hours per year without space heating, air conditioning or ventilation, hr/y

Impact of outer insulation thickness on thermal performance - BESOO 612:

- o positive impact on energy conservation
- o Massachusetts regulations for improving thermal insulation from R-25 to R-30 contribute 10% to energy conservation
- o further improvement of thermal insulation to R-35 will contribute 7% to energy conservation, and to R-40 - 12%
- o the contribution of outer insulation thickness to energy saving decreases from 3.3%/cm between R-25 and R-30, to 2.2%/cm between R-30 and R-40.
- o no impact on total comfort hours beyond R-30

Improving thermal insulation - conclusion

A change in thermal insulation from R-30 to R-35 and R-40 will result in energy savings of 7%-12% and a reduction of up to 1.2°C in the maximum Heat Index, but will not increase total comfort hours.

BESOO Website

This version of the Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization is available online (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESOO/611B>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESOO/612B>

<https://nowagreen.ct.ws/BESOO/644B>

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